

ISBN : 978-93-950596-0-7

Proceedings of
International Conference
on

“Embracing Change & Transformation-Breakthrough
Innovation and Creativity”

Edited by

**Dr. Amol Gawande
Dr. Atul Kumar**

DPU Dr. D. Y. Patil
B-School
Course Approved by AICTE, Ministry of HRD Govt. of India)

RELATIONSHIP MARKETING IMPLEMENTATION AND CUSTOMER RELATIONSHIP MANAGEMENT

Dr. Atul Kumar

Professor, Dr. D. Y. Patil B-School, Pune, Maharashtra, India

Abstract:

The implementation of the Customer Relationship Management (CRM) framework is a complex and daunting task that calls for the entire organisation to be improved. CRM is being introduced by more and more companies to achieve a sustainable competitive edge over competition. However, many of them do not achieve the expected performance or fail ultimately. The aim of this research is to assess what critical success factors (CSFs) influence the success of CRM deployment and how these CSFs can be effectively incorporated to help implement it. Another point is that during the implementation process for different companies these critical success factors can play a different role. Such CSFs should therefore be treated differently for individual companies.

Keywords: CRM, Partnership advertising, critical success factors

Introduction:

The marketing climate has dramatically changed in the last decade, including globalisation, ever-increasing competition, technology advancement, etc. Today customers want more shopping experience and want to be closely connected with suppliers. They have more options and their demands are changing rapidly. For the changing world, the old marketing strategy, one for mass marketing, does not suffice. The one-to-one marketing strategy is moving businesses over competitors in the direction of sustainable competitive advantage. For many companies and firms, the bulk of income comes from a limited number of loyal and successful customers. The Pareto rule shows that 20% of customers generate 80% of income. The main task for companies is therefore how to reach customers and attract successful customers. Partnership marketing and Customer Relationship Management Systems (CRMs) can help companies to achieve those goals. More and more companies are currently introducing CRM systems, but many of them do not attain the desired performance or even fail. One of the key factors is that the CRM programmes, instead of the whole organisational process and a long-term plan, are only considered by these organisations as a technical initiative or marketing project. In reality, companies should consider several critical success factors, including organisational structure, corporate culture, incentive system, training system etc, with holistic view of the implementation of the CRM system. This study aims to examine what important success factors impact the success of CRM implementation and how these CSFs are integrated into the implementation of companies.

Definition of the CRM Framework:

CRM systems are tools that allow companies to focus on customers and develop long-term, sustainable customer relationships. In the field of marketing, CRM is a relatively new idea, but writers and marketers have frequently related this concept over the last few years, paying increasing attention to the implementation of CRMs. Although they had a different understanding of this theory, they all thought it would be inevitable for CRM systems to be incorporated and to offer them significant future benefits.

Figure-1**What's a true CRM?**

CRM is not a technology or even a community of technologies, it is a continuously changing process and requires a different thinking from relying on the traditional business model internally. According to Morrel, S., and Philonenko. "CRM is a customer approach based on thoughtful investment in staff, technology and business processes." Kotler et al (2002) also indicated that CRM systems may include data warehouses that store all data of a company, customer services systems, e-commerce systems, e-marketing, operating systems (that handle order inputs, invoicing, payouts, point inputs, payments and the point input system). This concept can be better understood from a marketing and information technology perspective."

The organisations implementing CRM systems must be marketing customer-centered. During the transition from mass marketing to one-to-one marketing, companies should change their marketing philosophy. Kotler et al (2002) have expressed various ideologies: focus on development, product orientation, sales orientation, marketing orientation and societal orientation. The majority of companies now orient their products. This form of business assumes that the profits are derived from high goods quality. If only high-quality products are produced, consumers will buy them. However, this is not the issue. For today's consumers, there are different tastes and more options. In the future, therefore, companies that strive to achieve the highest results should follow a new marketing philosophy: social marketing which means that companies should take marketing decisions taking account of customer desires, business requirements, consumers' long-term interests, and society's long-term interests.

Kutner and Cripps (1997) said that CRM is based on four concepts:

1. Customers should be handled as significant assets.
2. Customers' profitability varies; not all customers are equally attractive.

3. Consumers differ in their wishes. Preferences, buying and price sensitivity measures

4. By recognising customer drivers and customer profitability, companies can personalise their products to optimise the full value of their consumer portfolio.

Curley (1999) divided CRM systems into four components from the information management perspective:

1. A data centre with customer, contract, transaction and network information.
2. Research tools for analysing the database and recognising customer actions patterns.
3. Campaign management tools that allow marketing department communication and the automated generation of such communications.
4. Communicate with the operating environment in order to manage the marketing database and contact networks to transmit the messages.

Kotler et al. (2002), also noted that 'CRM systems can be data warehoused stores that store all company information, customer service systems, call centres, e-commerce, web marketing, operating systems (which process order entry, invoicing, payments, outlets, inventory systems, etc.) and selling systems (mobile sales communications, appointment making, routing, etc.).'

In fact, information technology is indispensable for implementing CRM because it offers techniques and resources for gathering and evaluating customer information; efficient implementations are not possible without excellent CRM software. However, this does not mean that the technology is adequate and all problems can be resolved during the implementation process. It actually includes changes across the organisation, such as policy, structure, culture, job processes, reward schemes, managerial system, etc. CRM systems are capital investments that include policy, advertising, IT and all other corporate components.

Architecture of CRM:

Stan Maklan (1999) pointed out that technology, processes and new skills can be incorporated under an overall framework which allows the company to shift from "making and sell" to a "listen and support" strategy. The architecture of the CRM is the following:

The following table shows the CRM architecture

Stan Maklan (1999) said that five main areas can be divided into the CRM architecture:

- The integrated front office helps marketing, sales and customer support departments to draw a complete image of each customer's needs through the use of technology. Technologies include call centres, sales force outsourcing and the Internet.
- A market intelligence framework enables companies to understand consumers on the basis of customer experience and external data. This system can be further divided into two elements: mining and analytical storage systems and technology. Warehousing technology collects valuable customer information and prepares it. While mining and analysis tools enable companies to segment clients in accordance with customers' behaviour, motivation, cost and profitability.

- Business intelligence is passed through workflow and business rules to the centralised front office. Based on learning, customer contact gives front office workers powerful insights into the customer. These rules help front-office workers to meet their customers' needs.
- The physical connection to the back-office system enables the intelligent front office to access the latest back office data. The front office will then better sell goods and services to customers. An interactive front and back office dialogue in real time is considered best practise in CRM.
- Suitable performance management systems enable companies to see the value they offer to consumers and the value they generate for customers.

CRM implementation:

The CSF model was implemented in the implementation of ERP, Holland and Light (1999). (Enterprise Resource Planning). Now, many authors and managers assume that this model can drive the implementation of CRM. By implementing ERP, we will understand the key factors affecting the performance of CRM implementation.

Table.1 CSF Model

Strategic	Tactical
Legacy systems	Client consultation
Business vision	Personnel
ERP strategy	BPC and software configuration
Top management support	Client acceptance
Project schedule and plans	Monitoring and feedback
	Communication
	Trouble shooting

ERP Determination:

Holland and Light (1999) notes that, through the inclusion of best practises in prompt decision making, cost reduction, and more management, the ERP system automates key corporate activities such as manufacturing, human resources, finance, and supply chain management. ERP is a system that manages and meets all organisational needs of the organisation. A successful implementation of ERP can offer companies enormous advantages. However, unsuccessful implementation will be a disaster for companies. In order to effectively manage the implementation process, a critical success factors framework was developed

Success Critical Factor (CSF):

The following is the CSF model:

Figure-3

While the strategic and tactical variables are all important for the successful implementation of the project, they have a different impact on the project during different periods. Strategic players are more important at the beginning of implementation, while tactical factors are more important towards the end.

Use of ERP versus CRM:

Stone (2000) said business can be divided into headquarter and headquarters: the headquarters carries out customer-oriented duties, such as advertising, sales and marketing, customer service. The back office carries out corporate tasks such as supply chain, activities, human resources and outsourcing. ERP systems focus on internal processes and resource management and integrate back office functions. In contrast, CRM systems focus on front office integration, such as marketing, selling and customer service. In order to promote implementation, rather than just the implementation of technology, the implementation of these two systems must take the whole organisational change into account. There are many similarities in the way these two systems are implemented. Many companies use ERP systems to integrate and manage internal processes and believe that the Critical Success Factors (CSF) model will effectively support implementation. Many industries are implementing ERP systems successfully in the CSF model to manage the implementation process. Implementing the CRM system on the basis of the ERP system is helpful to companies.

The CSF for the implementation of CRM:

CRM implementation can gain a lot from previous initiatives on corporate change, like ERP and TQMM (Total Quality Management). Keith Thompson (2000) considered that "CRM can only be seen as another change programme, and the literature says it requires the same level of support and consistency as its predecessors:"

- Middle management alignment
- Align incentives and measures with the new attitudes desired.
- Integration of business systems into a common goal.
- Program management for energy maintenance, progress and obstacle overcoming.
- New information systems supporting new business processes.
- Mass participation and education of employees and suppliers.

However, the CRM system is very different from the ERP system, which focuses on "back office" and internal procedures. It has problems with the front office and is driven externally. Although the above-mentioned success factors remain necessary, they are not sufficient. Keith Thompson (2000) also said that changing the front office presents additional challenges:

- o The key player in the change programme, the customer, is not directly controlled by the enterprise.
- o Competitive offers to customers are also visible (resulting from their own CRM programmes).
- o It is difficult to pilot and implement new systems and processes carefully. These often come immediately into the public sphere and are subject to intensive scrutiny from the start.

- o There are financial costs for a back-office system initially delayed or unsuccessful, but which do not automatically lead to business loss. Some of your best clients may be driven away by a failing front office system, many of which will never return.

Align the organisation as a whole in support of CRM implementation:

Top managers during CRM implementation should carefully avoid two misconceptions. The first is that IT is a panacea and addresses all the problems that companies face. Secondly, the department of marketing is solely responsible for the CRM system. Without cooperation from other departments, marketing cannot complete this task. There is no doubt that the failure to implement these two opinions will be caused. CRM systems are implemented by changing the whole organisation. Therefore, this change should be managed by senior managers across the entire organisation, including structures, strategies, corporate culture, awards system, personnel and work processes. The failure will result in any component being neglected.

The Standard Model (Beckhard and Harris) will help companies manage CRM system implementation. The Standard Model is a well-known model for managing the organisational change process. This model raises three fundamental questions:

- o Right now, where are we? (What is our current state?)
- o Where should we be? (What is our future desired state?)
- o How are we going to get there? (How will we handle this transition?)

The first step is to understand the situation of the current organisation, including the current marketing approach, the information technology we now use; customers' needs and wants; the organization's resources, capabilities and competence, etc. After the transformation, top managers then set goals, including the future of the organisation; the approach to marketing; how to communicate with profitable customers; what benefits the change should bring, etc. There is a gap between the current situation and the future goals. In order to achieve these goals, top managers should integrate and coordinate the whole organisation to support change. The main and most challenging task is to manage these changes. Many considerations influence the implementation of CRM systems. However, some are more important than others.

Information technology: Information technologies

The marketing environment has significantly changed, and today's customers can no longer be treated as a homogenous collection, but as individuals with unique behaviours, such as buying patterns, use of channels etc. Information technology has for a long time been used to manage individual communication channels, including call centres, websites and emails. The technology enables the company to develop relationships with its customers in three aspects: first, customer databases help the company to remember a customer in particular, including its buying habits, preference and decision-making. Secondly, customers can interact with the business through technology to express their new demands and feelings for existing products. Thirdly, after communication with customers the company can customise its needs by making special offers for various customers. Effective technological components are key factors for implementing CRMs.

The maturity of technology, including hardware and software, makes it possible to analyse a huge amount of data at amazing speeds. Gilmore and Firing (2004) also pointed out that more and more companies now need software solutions to see and adjust their marketing process from the viewpoint of the whole company.

These software solutions help companies to optimise the value of the customer relationship via canals and product lines. The software also needs to facilitate business-consumer interaction. Many CRM application providers are now available on the CRM market. Software solutions come from three major vendors: marketing automation, sales force automation and customer support and field service. These approaches have been used to integrate customer contact points for front office applications.

There are many options for CRM software in the industry. Companies should therefore carefully consider their technology investments. On the one hand, it spending a lot on hardware and software solutions; on the other, various firms have different conditions such as current technology, employees' skills and capacities, etc. The installation of new technology is difficult for companies. Most companies fail. A series of studies on the success or failure of IT systems were cited by Leverick, Littler, Bruce and Wilson (1998): Only 11% of respondents said their installation in a survey of 400 British and Irish companies was successful. No significant benefits were achieved in another 30-40% of IT projects. Thompson et al (2000) also referred to a study which found that when they competed, "Three-quarters of IT projects either were unsuccessful or were not used." The main problem was the integration of new technology into existing systems

"There are several criteria for choosing the right technology: Firstly, the technology needs to give employees a clear view of the marketing process internally so that they use technology to offer better service to customers. Secondly, technology must help companies to collect customer information from all channels and transmit the marketing message to clients efficiently and quickly. In the communication process, interactive contact is extremely important. Thirdly, the new installed technology should be compatible with the old one. In short, a two-way dialogue, CRM technology, must be established. The value should be understood both by marketers and customers.

The trend towards CRM implementation now involves integrating all customer contact points. The most effective solution is to integrate and cooperate with multiple CRM technologies. For example, Gilmore and Firing (2004) suggested "Often the integration of best breed technologies will be the best path." A company can choose to use Vignette to adapt, Personify for automated rule generation and Siebel for call centre and back office integration. However, the application of technology alone is not enough and companies must combine IT with a philosophy that requires a reorganisation of the company as a whole around its customers. "The other obstacles that prevent IT systems from being adopted include lack of a clear strategy, budget restrictions, long implementation times; management priority; resistance to change and lack of user knowledge and training," Littlewood (1999) noted. Littlewood. This shift is not easy to achieve. In order to achieve a balance of new technologies and firm changes such as culture, structure, process, recompense system and so on, strong, enduring and profitable relationships with stable customer bases have been established.

Process Organization:

As these organisations focus on products or market shares rather than customers, traditional organisations cannot implement relationship marketing and CRM effectively. To facilitate the implementation of CRM, companies need a new style of organisation. In addition to maintaining its functional excellence in marketing, sales, R&D and manufacturing, it focuses on the process which adds value to the client. A business process is a collection of associated value-making activity, such as research, production, delivery, after-sales services, marketing and so on. Today's customers are stronger and more demanding. Neither function can generate added value to satisfy consumers alone. Therefore, process organisations tend to coordinate cross-functional behaviours while remain dependent on functionality quality. Because process organisations operate cross-functionally, they are better equipped to satisfy customer requirements than functional and matrix organisations. Therefore, process organisations are more likely to retain customers.

Process management enables companies to provide their customers with better, cheaper, faster and closer service. For example, the most important thing when customer preference changes is to at least produce new products on the market. Since each department must complete its own task before the next one can start, traditional organisations have difficulty reducing market time. Organizing the processes

This problem can be solved properly. The time for the marketing of functional organisation and process organisation is as follows:

Lynette Ryals (2000) pointed out that certain opinions have to be noticed during the transition from traditional organisation to process organisation. First, process organisations are very customer-focused and view the customer relationship as an important asset instead of a cost. They want to invest in the marketing of the future business. In contrast to process organisers, functional organisations often consider marketing as a cost and tend to reduce their marketing budget in difficult times; it's ironic that this is where investment is most needed. Secondly, customer profitability is the fundamental concept of customer relationship management. Traditional enterprises erroneously believe that revenue is derived from goods and only notice production. However, customer-focused companies believe that profits derive from customers and create systems to measure and manage customer profitability.

The corporate structure:

Bhide says "An organization's ability to implement its strategy depends on its "hard" infrastructure, organisation, systems and "soft" infrastructure, culture and standards." Perhaps the most important resource of the organisation is the people. Consequently, the success of the strategy depends on the role played by individuals, how they interact through formal and informal processes and the relations they build. The entire organisational configuration determines how business strategies are implemented. The configuration consists of the systems, procedures, interactions and limits that the company works through. Chandler (1962) believed that his strategy shapes forms of organisational structure. The structure will support or hinder the strategy's implementation. Many companies believe that marketing relations and CRM systems will bring them a sustainable competitive edge and significant advantages. While

planned carefully by some companies due to the organisational structure, the relationship marketing and CRM cannot be successfully carried out. Therefore, if companies decide to implement a CRM system, they must fit their organisational structure into their strategy.

Instead of being "functionally focused," organisations are gradually being "process-oriented," which usually means that businesses have a holistic view and see the connection between their activities rather than focusing on separate functions and tasks. The whole company must ensure at the moment that marketing goals are achieved and that mutually profitable customer relationships are established.

Cost centres or profit centres in conventionally organised structures, such as a functional structure, product structure or matrix structure can be individual departments. Each function only focuses on products or their own performance. Individual functions rarely take account of the company's long-term profits and performance by providing customers with added value and making them satisfied and loyal.

Nonetheless, customer-focused organisations highlight cross-functional customer relations. Lynette Ryals (2000) stated that the general responsibility for customer profitability lies with cross-functional customer management teams. The customer management team may wish to offer the customer a portfolio to increase the overall profitability of the relationship. Some of this portfolio requires one or more individual functions for cost reduction or customization of products, cost reduction or profit reduction. They are unwilling to do this at a single cost or profit centre because their own performance is damaged by the behaviour. Therefore, the cross-functional customer management team is crucial for implementing CRM in a customer-driven organisation.

The Organization's culture:

Culture can contribute or hinder the successful implementation of strategies. A close relationship between culture and strategy promotes effective strategic implementation. Nelson and Quick (1994) suggested that corporate culture works as a mechanism for controlling how employees are shaped. Corporate culture is thus considered to be one of the key determinants of corporate performance. It is helpful for organisations to develop a sense of commitment to the organization's goal by effectively managing organisational culture. Moreover, organisational culture is a very important factor that determines whether the organisational change succeeds or not. Companies need to create a corporate culture that promotes customers. All employees are committed to ensuring their customers' satisfaction, loyalty to their organisation and products, and good customer relations. Additional training for staff

The adoption of new performance criteria may be involved. For instance, a business that wishes to maximise customer profitability for life needs to educate its individuals about the difference between maximising short-term profits and creating long-term value.

Individuals Management:

Individuals are vital to the strategy. Knowledge and experience of people can be key factors for successful strategies. The human resources management system can help or

hinder the implementation of a new strategy. Most organisations regard people as their most important asset. They deployed, managed, managed and encouraged people to develop business strategies. First, organisations are developing new strategies for the future and the HR requirements are assessed to support the new strategies. Secondly, organisations should identify the current knowledge, skills and abilities of employees and clarify the gap between existing capabilities and future needs. Third, organisations select the right people and make the skills of people adaptable to the demand for new strategies through recruitment, training, evaluation and reward.

Through the short-term cycle of HR objectives, performance assessments, rewards and training, HR strategies must be able to underpin the current strategies of an organisation, while simultaneously transforming the organisation and forming a platform that will allow new strategies to emerge through the long-term cycle of HR issues

-skills, culture, leadership

System of Rewarding:

Most managers believe that nothing will be changed if the reward system does not change. "If you talk about change, but not change the system of recognition and rewards, nothing changes," said Paul Allaire (CEO, Xerox Corp). Reward systems are the most powerful tool for strategic engagement. The existing reward systems must align employee behaviour with the goals of the whole organisation. Jochen Sengpiehl (2004) researched and developed CRM in several industries, including some key factors and key obstacles.

Key Success Factors	CRM-Main Barriers
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Clear scope definition and TOP-Management agreement is fundamental - Integration of all customer touch points and strategic stakeholders from the beginning - Clear process definition will cover all CRM modules regarding content, data and system requirements as well as responsibilities - Step by step transformation from a product-oriented organization towards a customer centric organization - Align currently divided marketing department towards CRM (organization and CRM budget in one responsibility) - Centralize where possible - Penetrate importance of CRM through continuous information and internal communication - CRM-Pilot is essential before 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Most CRM-activities are stand-alone solutions - No consistent CRM concept and strategy - Missing agreement of Top-management - Missing understanding and internal acceptance of CRM (short term versus long term) - Many companies are still product driven and not customer oriented - Skills and competence at the dealer level about CRM are often very low - Organisational and cultural barriers within global brands are very high - CRM Dealer processes usually not defined - Right of data ownership and data usage - Lack of resources

implementing total CRM- Approach - Conduct training sessions.	- eCRM is usually not integrated - Usually no integrated and consistent IT- and database across all CRM modules
--	--

The success of the CRM relationships is influenced by many factors, such as a good plan, technology support, top management support, corporate structure, staff, the payroll system, etc. However, these variables play different roles for various industries and enterprises in the process of CRM implementation.

Large Companies:

There are several important points that should be noticed for large companies, like Tesco. Firstly, it is necessary to evaluate the role of information technology in the implementation of CRM. These large companies are always too worried and depend on technology's role and invest heavily in software. The technology is, of course, essential in order to implement the CRM. However, technology is not the whole thing. Just like Tesco, why is the implementation of CRM successful? It is not only because of the installation of some advanced software. The most important thing is how this information can be transferred to the whole organisation, how employees can understand this message and respond as soon as possible after collecting customer information from the 'Tesco.com' website or the head office staff. In order to satisfy customers, the entire organisation should participate. The company should understand that information technology is not a panacea and cannot solve all problems during the CRM implementation process. Another point to be noted is that before investing in new software, companies should consider whether the new technology is compatible with the current one. Moreover, companies need to understand software employees' skills and knowledge. If they are not qualified and unable to use new technology, companies should provide them with the training they need.

The second and possibly most difficult problem for large companies is whether or not the existing organisational structure supports the implementation of CRM. We realise that large companies always have a complex structure and are inflexible to respond to the transition. CRM management requires companies to integrate the front office and back office departments, in contrast to other project management firms, such as ERP and TQM. However, different departments may be different centre types. For instance, sales marketing can be a profit centre, while a cost centre can be a supply department. To make more profit, marketing wants to sell more products, and it needs to buy better quality products from the supply department. The procurement department, however, is a cost centre. They focus on how costs can be reduced instead of how customers can be satisfied.

Conflicts therefore exist between the different departments. Sometimes these conflicts cannot be resolved. The most important task during the CRM implementation process is how conflicts between various centres can be coordinated. For some industries, especially for the retail industry, interactive activity with suppliers is of equal importance than with customers. Retailers should establish good relationships with suppliers to implement CRM systems successfully.

Retailers are re-sellers of products and services, add value to them and make them available to the final customer of the shopping as mentioned above "close" and convenient. They do not produce products on their own. Therefore, distributors must promptly send data to their suppliers after they understand the needs of customers. Then the suppliers deliver goods and services quickly as retailers request. In addition, a good long-term relationship with suppliers will increase retailers' negotiating power and reduce costs. The excellent relationship between customers and retailers provides customers with greater advantages. Some software, such as the electronic data interchange (EDI), has been installed by retailer giants, Tesco and Wal-Mart to make orders and to interact with their suppliers electronically. This programme covers prediction, scheduling, refilling and shipping applications. This software is important because retailers can send sales information on a daily basis to their selected key suppliers. This software enables distributors and their manufacturers to plan stock levels, generate purchase orders and deliver when needed.

Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs):

These critical success factors should be taken into account differently for small businesses when implementing the CRM system. First, small businesses should understand clearly the project's mission and develop a detailed plan for managing the process of implementation of the CRM. How to manage a project which is always determined by the boss itself in small companies, particularly small companies in developing countries. There is no formal and systematic strategy or plan. This means that the whole organisation has no clear idea how the CRM system can be implemented. These small companies sometimes underestimate the importance of information technology, unlike large companies. You are not prepared to invest in the software and believe that money is wasted. These small enterprises believed they had a smaller group of customers than large companies and did not have to use special software to manage customers. That's a wrong and dangerous view. Small businesses' structure is simple and versatile. For top management, it is easy to coordinate the conflict between different departments. However, the interaction between various departments and employees may not be as good as expected. Moreover, as staff are at the heart of CRM implementation, small enterprises should give more attention to employee training.

Strengths and Weaknesses of SMEs

Strengths	Weaknesses
More customer focused	Poorer access to finance
More responsive to market needs	Resource constraints
Highly visible top management	Lack of high caliber staff
Low bureaucracy	Lack of skills
Informal working environment	Lower job security
Innovativeness	Less strategic thinking
Quick to seize opportunities	Less strategic planning
Flexibility	Lower standardization

Figure-4

Conclusion:

CRM implementation, including IT, strategy, corporate structure, culture, work process, the reward system and so on, is a complete corporate development. The Critical Success Factors (CSF) model can help companies manage the process of CRM implementation. During the CRM implementation process, two incorrect views have to be avoided; otherwise, the implementation of CRM will eventually fail. First, many managers overestimate technology and believe that technology can solve all problems during the implementation process. Technology is indeed the foundation of CRM, but it must be accompanied by other parts of the organisation to achieve this aim. In addition, implementing CRM is not the only task for the marketing department. This transition should involve all sections of the organisation. And this change should also be taken into account in all parts of the organisation. Moreover, some actors are more important for different businesses than others. They have a complex organisational structure for large companies, for example. Therefore, they should emphasise how different departments are aligned to achieve the goals. Technology and the knowledge of employees may prevent small and medium-sized enterprises from implementing a CRM system. Therefore, during the CRM implementation process, different companies should consider these factors differently, depending on their circumstances.

References

1. Chandler, A.D. (1962). *Strategy and Structure: Chapters in the History of American Enterprises*, Cambridge: MIT Press.
2. Christopher, M., Payne, A., & Ballantyne, D. (1998). *Relationship Marketing: Bringing Quality, Customer Service, and Marketing Together*. Oxford: Butterworth Heinemann.
3. Cooper D.R., & Emory C.W. (1995). *Business Research Methods*, (5 th Ed.), Chicago: Irwin
4. Corbae, G., Jensen, J.B., & Schneider, D. (2001). *Marketing 2.0: Strategies for Closer Customer Relationships*, Springer-Verlag, Berlin-Heidelberg.
5. Couldwell, C. (1999). Loyalty bonuses. *Marketing Week*, February 18.
6. Curley, B. (1999). Profiting from the Relationship. *Insurance and Technology*, 24 (3):34-38.
7. Dowling, G.(2002). Customer Relationship Management: In B2C Markets, Often Less is More. *California Management Review*, 44(3):87-104.
8. Ernst & Young. (2001). UK Retail: What stakeholders need to know.[online] Available: [http://www.ey.com/global/download.nsf/UK/Sharing_Knowledge_UK_retail/\\$file/9227_uk_retailweb.pdf](http://www.ey.com/global/download.nsf/UK/Sharing_Knowledge_UK_retail/$file/9227_uk_retailweb.pdf)
9. Esteves, J., Casanovas, J., & Pastor, J. (2003). Modeling with Partial Least Squares Critical Success Factors Interrelationships in ERP Implementations, Ninth Americas Conference on Information Systems, 446-451
10. Friends of the Earth. (2003). Super markets or corporate bullies, [Online] Available: www.foe.co.uk/resource/briefings/
11. Gilmore, D. & Firing, B. (2004). CRM Technology - A Primer.[Online] available: www.ogilvy.com/viewpoint/pdf/v3_gilmore_firing.pdf

12. Gordon I.H. (1998). Relationship Marketing: New Strategies, Techniques and Technologies to Win the Customers You Want and Keep Them Forever. John Wiley & Sons Canada.
13. Grönroos, C., (1994). From marketing mix to relationship marketing: Towards a paradigm shift in marketing. *Management decision*, 32(2), 4-20.
14. Gummesson, E. (2001). *Total Relationship Marketing: Rethinking Marketing Management: From 4Ps to 30Rs*, Oxford: Butterworth-Heinemann.
15. Holland, C., & Light, B. (1999). A Critical Success Factors Model for ERP Implementation. *IEEE Software*, May/June 1999.
16. Janjicek, R.(2003). CRM architecture for enterprise relationship marketing in the new millennium, technical white paper. [Online] Available http://h71028.www7.hp.com/enterprise/downloads/CRMArchitecture_Whitepaper_HPC.pdf
17. Johnson, G. & Scholes, K.,(2002). *Exploring Corporate Strategy*.(6thEd.), Harlow: Prentice Hall.
18. Kotler, P., Armstrong, G., Saunders, J. & Wong, V. (2001). *Principles of Marketing*, (3rd European Ed.), Financial Times/Prentice Hall.
19. Kutner, S. & Crpps, J.(1997). Managing the Customer Portfolio of Healthcare Enterprises. *The Healthcare Forum Journal*, 40 (5), 52-54.
20. Leidecker J.K. & Bruno A.V. (1987).CSF analysis and the strategy development process. In *Strategic Planning and Management Handbook*, New York, NY: Van Nostr and Rheinhold, 333-351.
21. Lidstone, J.(2003). Customer Loyalty-Pile it High and Prosper. [Online] Available: http://profesores.ie.edu/enrique_dans/tesco/pile%20it%20high.pdf Littlewood, F.(1999). Driven by technology. *Marketing*, March 11th,29-31
22. Malhotra, N.K. (1996). *Marketing Research: an applied orientation*, (2nded). New Jersey: Prentice Hall.
23. Maddali, P. (2004). Tesco in 2003. *Global CEO*, 6, 65-79.
24. Michaels, L. (2004). Strip lights, endless queues of strangers and shelves of packets, fake smiles from bored checkout assistants-isn't there a better way to get our food?. [Online] Available:<https://corporatewatch.org/sites/default/files/supermarkets.pdf>.
25. Morrel, S. & Philonenko, L.(2001). *20:20 CRM: A Visionary Insight into Unique Customer Contact*, San Francisco: Genesys Telecommunications Laboratories Inc.
26. Nelson, D. L.,& Quick J. C.(1994). *Organizational Behaviour: Foundations, realities and Challenges*, St. Paul, West
27. Palmer, A.(2000). *Principles of Marketing*, Oxford: Oxford University Press.
28. Peck, H., Payne, A., Christopher, M.,& Clark, M.(2004). *Relationship Marketing: Strategy and Implementation*, Burlington: Butterworth Heinemann.
29. Persson, P. (2004). Customer Relationship Management: How a CRM system can be used in the sales process. Master of thesis, Luth University of Technology, [Online] Available: <http://epubl.luth.se/1402-1617/2004/124/index-en.html>
30. Rockart J.(1979). Chief Executives Define Their Own Information Needs, *Harvard Business Review*, March 1979, 81-92

31. Ryals L., Thompson, K., Knox S., et al. (2000). Developing relationship marketing through the implementation of customer relationship management technology. Paper presented at the 16th Annual IMP International Seminar, Bath.
32. Schramm, W. (1971). Notes on case studies of instructional media projects. Working paper for the Academy for Educational Development, Washington, DC
33. Sengpiehl, J.(2004). Customer Relationship Management: Case Studies. BBDO consulting. [Online] Available: www.bbdo-interone.de/de/home/studien.ar.0022.Link1Download.tmp/crmcasestudies.pdf
34. Slevin, D.P & Pinto, J.K.(1987). Balancing Strategy and Tactics in Project Implementation, Sloan Management Review, 29, 33-41
35. Srinivasa, R.P. &Swarup, S. (2002). Business Intelligence and Retailing: Applications of data warehousing and data mining in the retail industry. [Online] Available:
http://searchdatabase.techtargget.com/whitepaperPage/0,293857,sid13_gci813866,00.html
36. Stone, M., Woodcock, N., &Machtynger, L.(2000). Customer Relationship Marketing: Get to know your customers and win their loyalty. London: Kogan.
37. Swift, R.(2001). Accelerating Customer Relationships Using CRM and relationship Technologies. New York: Prentice-Hall.
38. Woodcock, N., Ekinci, Y., &Stone, M.(2004). What impact does Customer Management really have on Business performance. [Online] Available:
http://www.qci.co.uk/public_face/Content/Impact%20of%20CM%20on%20Busines%20Performance.pdf
39. Yin, R.K. (2006). Case Study Research: Design and Methods. (3 rd Ed.),Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
40. Zikmund, W. (2000). Business Research Methods.(6th Ed.),TX: Dryden Press.

ABOUT THE CONFERENCE

Creativity and innovations are indispensable for the growth of business and the success of the organization. It is an important factor which helps traditional companies and educational institutions in foreseeing the potential threats and rising competition. Needless to say, companies and organizations cannot thrive without matching the pace with the change and transformation which is taking place in the market. Digital transformation integrates digital technologies into all areas of a business. To meet with the ever changing demands of business processes and customer expectations and create a competitive advantage as well as positioning the organization for the future growth, the role of digital transformation and innovation cannot be ignored. IoT, Artificial Intelligence (AI), Automation, Machine Learning, Block Chain are some of the latest technologies which have brought about the sea of change by amalgamating demanding millennial generation into the high speed data lanes. In the past few months of Lockdown, digitalization has played a vital role in sustaining the global economic condition. Businesses are now looking for the new ways of dealings and cost minimization. Educational institutions also embraced digital mode of teaching and learning methodologies in order to minimize the impact of pandemic on the academics of students. This conference is intended to seek intellectual contribution of experts from industry, academia and research for embracing change & transformation through innovations and creativity.

ABOUT US

Dr. D. Y. Patil B-School runs AICTE approved PGDM program. It has been ranked 1st Emerging B-School among top institutes of west India by Time of India. It has also been conferred the ET Now Business School of the year award. The two-year full-time PGDM program offered by Dr. D. Y. Patil B-School is designed to empower students to become successful business professionals in the challenging global scenario. The Institute is continually evolving to meet its goals in an ever-changing business environment. It has been playing an important role in professionalizing Indian Management through its programs. Dr. D. Y. Patil B-School aims to create value-driven leaders, global managers and entrepreneurs with strong conceptual foundations and analytical approach to help them be the best in whichever field they choose. The aim is to innovatively address the needs of a modern India and connecting aspirations and realities to attain benchmarks that are respected internationally.

Dr. D. Y. Patil B-School

Sr. No. 87-88, Bengaluru-Mumbai Express Bypass,

Tathawade, Pune - 411033, Maharashtra, India

+91-20-67919470 +91- 9975761235

info.bschool@dpu.edu.in